

LANGUAGE GAME IN BUSINESS ADVERTISING DISCOURSE: BASED ON ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE ADVERTISING

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Abstract:

This research investigates the phenomenon of language game in business advertising discourse with a contrastive analysis on English and Uzbek advertisements. Advertising, as one of the most influential types of discourse in modern society, employs various linguistic strategies to attract attention, persuade, and create memorable messages. Among these strategies, language game creative manipulation of words, sounds, and structures plays a crucial role. By analyzing samples from English and Uzbek business advertising, this study shows similarities and differences in the use of phonetic, lexical, semantic, and pragmatic language games. The findings highlight how cultural context, linguistic structure, and market orientation shape advertising creativity in both languages.

Keywords: language game, advertising discourse, English, Uzbek, wordplay, persuasion

Аннотация:

Данное исследование посвящено феномену языковой игры в дискурсе бизнес-рекламы и представляет собой сопоставительный анализ английских и узбекских рекламных текстов. Реклама, являясь одним из наиболее влиятельных видов дискурса в современном обществе, использует различные лингвистические стратегии для привлечения внимания, убеждения и создания запоминающихся сообщений. Среди этих стратегий особую роль играет языковая игра — креативная манипуляция словами, звуками и структурами. Анализ образцов английской и узбекской бизнес-рекламы демонстрирует сходства и различия в использовании фонетических, лексических, семантических и прагматических языковых игр. Полученные результаты подчеркивают, что культурный контекст, языковая структура и рыночная ориентация формируют специфику рекламного креатива в обоих языках.

Ключевые слова: языковая игра, рекламный дискурс, английский язык, узбекский язык, игра слов, убеждение.

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu tadqiqot biznes reklamasi diskursida til o'yini hodisasini ingliz va o'zbek reklamalarining qiyosiy tahlili asosida o'rganadi. Reklama, zamonaviy jamiyatdagi eng ta'sirchan diskurs turlaridan biri sifatida, e'tiborni tortish, ishontirish va esda qolarli xabarlar yaratishda turli lingvistik strategiyalardan foydalanadi. Ushbu strategiyalar orasida so'zlar, tovushlar va tuzilmalar bilan ijodiy munosabatga asoslangan til o'yini muhim o'rin tutadi. Ingliz va o'zbek biznes reklamalaridan olingan namunalar tahlili fonetik, leksik, semantik va pragmatik til o'yinlaridan foydalanishdagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari madaniy kontekst, til tuzilishi va bozor yo'nalishi har ikkala tilda ham reklama kreativligini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etishini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'yini, reklama diskursi, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili, so'z o'yini, ishontirish.

Introduction:

Advertising discourse is a powerful medium through which businesses communicate their messages to consumers. It employs various linguistic techniques to make advertisements more appealing, memorable, and persuasive.¹ Among these techniques, the language game plays a pivotal role in engaging audiences and influencing their purchasing decisions. This research aims to examine the linguistic features of the language game in English and Uzbek advertisements, drawing on theoretical perspectives from renowned linguists and advertising researchers. According to M.A. Ivanova, "A successful businessman does not take hasty actions that may lead to uncertain results – all his actions, including his speech, must be carefully planned. That is, speech, too, must be thoroughly planned, taking into account the specific features of the situation and the possible ways of developing events, with a deliberate selection of actions and means intended to draw attention."² Communication (both horizontal and vertical) is considered an integral aspect of the work process. In the study of business discourse, the process of communication is viewed not as a mere exchange of information, but rather as the recipient's participation in the sphere of interaction with the world in order to exert influence directed toward

¹ Azimova D.A "Language game in advertising discourse: based on English and Uzbek language advertising"
"Zamonaviy Tilshunoslik va Tarjimashunoslikning dolzarb muammolari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman.
Toshkent. 2025

² Иванова М.А. Особенности аббревиатур делового дискурса через призму профессиональной языковой личности бизнесмена // Гуманитарные, социально-экономические и общественные науки. – Краснодар: Наука и образование, 2014. – Вып. 10. – С. 158.

that person. In other words, in one way or another, the recipient of the message alters the state of the environment in which they are situated and generates a behavioral response that corresponds to the goals of the listeners. It should be especially emphasized that the diversity of approaches to defining and studying business discourse reflects the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon. As evidence of this idea, we would like to present several definitions of business discourse found in the works of both foreign and local researchers.

According to the Russian linguist V.I. Karasik, "... business discourse is limited to the professional activity of entrepreneurs and constitutes speech aimed at reaching a mutually beneficial agreement on the business issue under discussion."³

Language game, a term originating from Wittgenstein's philosophy and later developed in linguistic pragmatics, refers to playful, intentional, and strategic deviations from ordinary language use. It includes puns, rhymes, neologisms, phonetic manipulation, code-switching, and metaphorical reconceptualizations. In business advertising, such linguistic play is used to increase memorability, create emotional impact, and influence consumer behavior.

The purpose of this research is to explore how language games function in English and Uzbek business advertisements, and what cultural-linguistic factors determine their specific forms.

The research is based on contrastive discourse analysis. A corpus of 100 advertisements (50 in English, 50 in Uzbek) from business sectors such as banking, retail, and technology has been collected from newspapers, online platforms, and television. Qualitative content analysis is applied to identify language games, while a pragmatic framework is used to assess their communicative effect.

³ Карасик В.И. О типах дискурса // Языковая личность: институциональный и персональный дискурс: Сб. науч. тр. – Волгоград: Перемена, 2000. – С. 5-20.

Findings and Discussion

Types of language game in English and Uzbek advertising are analyzed and showed cultural peculiarities in the following sentences. Firstly in English advertisements: **Phonetic play**: rhyme, alliteration (e.g., “Coca-Cola – Open Happiness”). **Wordplay or puns**: polysemy, homonymy (e.g., “Nothing runs like a Deere”). **Neologisms or blending**: “Breathalyzer,” “Frappuccino.”

Code-switching: use of foreign words for prestige (“Dolce Vita” perfumes).

Secondly, In Uzbek advertisements there are also numerous types and of language Game in Uzbek Advertising: **Phonetic play**: alliteration, reduplication (“Shirin – shirindan ham shirin”). **Semantic play**: proverbs and cultural metaphors adapted to products. **Metaphor**: Sweetness -Happiness, Hospitality. **(Chocolate brand)**: “*Har bir mehmoningizga shirin tabassum Sfad bilan.*” (A sweet smile for every guest with Sfad.) **Proverb play for tech product**: “*Vaqt oltindan qadrl.*” **Ad adaptation (Smartphone brand)**, “*Oltin vaqtini Xiaomi bilan tejang.*” (Save your golden time with Xiaomi.) **Hybrid forms**: Uzbek-English blends in modern ads (“Smart Kredit – tez va easy”). **Word creation**: use of suffixes to form catchy brand names (“Navro‘z tea,” “Do‘stona Bank”). English advertising rely more on brevity, rhyme, and global cultural references. Uzbek ads often integrate national identity, proverbs, and emotional-cultural appeals. Code-switching is common in Uzbek due to English’s prestige as a global business language. Both contexts use humor and creativity, but linguistic economy in English contrasts with poetic tradition in Uzbek. Language games enhance memorability, emotional appeal, and persuasive effect. In Uzbek culture, appeal to tradition and collectivist values strengthens trust, while in English advertising, humor and modernity dominate.

Conclusion

Language game is a universal feature of advertising discourse but is shaped by cultural and linguistic context. English advertising tends toward globalized, witty, and concise forms, while Uzbek advertising reflects cultural resonance, proverb-based creativity, and hybrid language use. Understanding these features is crucial not only for linguists but also for practitioners in marketing and intercultural communication.

References:

1. Cook, G. (1992). The Discourse of Advertising. London: Routledge.
2. Leech, G. (1966). English in Advertising. London: Longman.
3. Goddard, A. (2002). The Language of Advertising. London: Routledge.
4. Wittgenstein, L. Philosophical Investigations. Blackwell. 1953

- 5.Иванова М.А. Особенности аббревиатур делового дискурса через призму профессиональной языковой личности бизнесмена//Гуманитарные, социально- экономические и общественные науки. – Краснодар: Наука и образование, 2014. – Вып. 10. – С. 158.
- 6.Карасик В.И. О типах дискурса // Языковая личность: институциональный и персональный дискурс: Сб. науч. тр. – Волгоград: Перемена, 2000. – С. 5-20.
- 7.Karimov, A. (2018). Reklama matnlarida til o'yini va uslubiy vositalar. Toshkent.
- 8.Azimova D.A "Language game in advertising discourse: based on English and Uzbek language advertising" "Zamonaviy Tilshunoslik va Tarjimashunoslikning dolzarb muammolari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman. Toshkent. 2025

